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History of money supply of military personnel (in the case of Russia)

Abstract: this article describes the concept and evolution of money supply of military personnel. In addition, the nature, principles, functions and structure of military allowances are analyzed. In addition, the evolution of the payment system for military personnel is covered in detail.

Key words: military serviceman, financial support, material support, evolution, material support, monetary allowance, military service, social support.

In scientific and legal literature, as well as in official statements of political and public figures, the current state of monetary allowance is assessed at a very low level that does not correspond to the nature and importance of the tasks performed by military personnel. At the same time, there is no single point of view in assessing the necessary and sufficient level of funds. At present, there have been few attempts to study the nature of monetary allowances for military personnel, organizational and legal guarantees, and the procedure for timely and complete delivery to each military personnel, as well as the powers of the state from a separate regulatory and legal point of view. bodies in the field of military service by citizens and military administration bodies, the right to fair remuneration for work in terms of consistency and efficiency. At the same time, all these issues require careful study and understanding. This applies especially to the issues of creating a new structure of payment for military servicemen, providing conditions for them to live a decent life, adequately covering all the difficulties and risks of military service, limiting their rights and freedoms. There is no doubt that it will be more effective if the work on increasing the salary of military personnel is carried out on a scientific basis. The object of research is the system of cash benefits for military personnel. The subject of research is financial and economic relations that determine the amount and structure of military allowances, the order of their delivery to recipients, as well as legal guarantees of timely and complete satisfaction with this type of assistance.

Achieving the goal includes solving the following tasks: • Studying the essence, content of the current legislation of the Russian Federation, the mechanism for determining the amount and procedure for paying military allowances to military personnel; • to study the history of the development of monetary allowances for military personnel from the tsarist army to the present state; • Review of powers of state bodies of the Russian Federation and military command and control bodies in the field of legal regulation of funds for military personnel and determination of conflicts; • to study the specific features of determining the amount of military payments in the context of socio-economic changes in society and military reforms; • analysis of the main trends in the development of legislation in the field of monetary benefits in modern times; • developing proposals for improving the legal regulation of military service pay; • developing proposals for improving the salary structure and level of military personnel.

The methodological basis of the research is the general scientific dialectical method of knowledge and scientific methods: historical, logical, sociological, systematic-structural, comparative legal, etc. General logical methods of knowledge (analysis, synthesis, generalization) are also used in the research. with their help, the existing legalities in the field of state-legal events, problems and ways to improve the legal regulation of monetary allowances for military personnel are identified. The legal basis of the research is the

Constitution of the Russian Federation, the Budget Code of the Russian Federation, Federal Laws "On Defense", "On the Status of Military Servicemen", other federal laws, decrees and orders of the President of the Russian Federation. The Russian Federation, decisions of the Government of the Russian Federation, regulatory legal documents of the federal executive authorities, as well as orders of the Minister of Defense of the Russian Federation regulating the issue of monetary allowances to military personnel. The theoretical importance of the work is determined by the development of rules, conclusions and proposals that have a certain scientific novelty, including the determination of the nature of military servicemen's monetary allowances, the definition, determination and analysis of the legal mechanisms for the formation of its composition and amounts. Functions of the state bodies of the Russian Federation, military command and control bodies in this field in terms of their completeness, consistency and efficiency.

The nature, principles, functions and structure of monetary allowances for military personnel. Currently, a clear understanding of the monetary supply system for military personnel and its elements is not given, and their content has not been studied. Legal regulation of the procedure for determining the amount of benefits for military personnel needs research. "System" (from the Greek Systema - composed of parts, connected) is a set of elements that interact and communicate with each other and form a certain wholeness, unity. Analysis of current legislation and scientific literature allows to talk about the concept of monetary system in a narrow and broad sense. In a narrow sense, the salary system for military personnel is a set of principles, methods and methods for calculating, determining and changing the salary, allowances and other additional payments provided by law for military personnel. It should be taken into account that the established mechanism for the formation of monetary allowance and its delivery to specific military personnel is carried out through the entry into legal relations of the relevant subjects. The generality of this type of legal relationship, in turn, should be included in the system of monetary benefits. Therefore, in a broad sense, the salary system can be defined as a system of legal relations related to the determination and implementation of payment to military personnel in accordance with laws and other regulatory legal documents.

In legal and military literature, there is no uniform definition of the monetary allowance of military personnel. In determining the nature of money, the authors use different approaches and consider individual aspects of this social phenomenon. Thus, in the Military Encyclopedia, monetary allowance is defined as an integral part of financial support aimed at meeting the personal material needs of the troops, provided to them by the state in the form of regular payments of money, according to the official duties performed. On the other hand, financial support means a set of activities organized and carried out in order to timely and fully meet the needs of troops (forces) for funds, including financial planning and financing; request, receive, store, spend economically and appropriately, control their use, record and report. Thus, the important points in the given definition are, firstly, the funds are the financial support of the troops, that is, the activities of the competent authorities in the process of financing the costs of maintaining the troops, and secondly, in the definition, the purpose of funds, in particular: to meet the personal material needs of troops (military personnel). Starov B.F. and Kuznetsov N.I. In the textbook, the Military Administration indicates that monetary compensation is the payment of monetary rewards to military personnel for performing military service and military duties. In this case, the authors emphasize that in determining the salary of military personnel, it is directly related to the performed military service duties. The authors of the Legal Reference on the issue of cash benefits to military personnel are of the

same opinion. Other authors, in determining the monetary allowance of military personnel, emphasize that it is an integral part of the material support of military personnel and, unlike natural types of pension, is aimed at meeting the monetary needs of military personnel. All the above points of view deserve the right to exist and do not contradict each other in any way.

In recent years, the modern Russian state and Russian society have significantly intensified efforts to restore the traditional high meaning of the concepts of "statesman", "sovereign man" in Russia. For this purpose, state regulatory measures are used in various spheres of public relations: state-legal, political, economic, informational, cultural, and others. At the moment, measures are being developed to increase the prestige of military service and strengthen military discipline in the troops. In the legislation of the Russian Federation, clarifications on the procedure of military service, improvement of the system of social guarantees for military personnel, etc. are ongoing.

Historical experience in increasing Russia's influence in solving the most pressing issues of modern military development, and the appeal of military service is of particular interest. For the first time, "military manpower" measures were implemented in the middle of the 15th century. Warriors were always under the special attention and patronage of princely (state) authorities. For their conscientious service, they received plots of land that were leased to free peasants during military service. Provision of a detachment until the middle of the 16th century, it was done by collecting a certain tribute from the artisans and peasants of the city. It was created in the 50s of the 16th century. Streltsy troops armed themselves and underwent annual centralized training at the expense of the treasury. Military service exempted archers from the burden of taxation and protected them from the risk of becoming indentured servants or serfs. To compensate for the hardships and privations of military service, the state granted the archers the right to engage in crafts and trade, and also provided them with land. Since the 17th century, social guarantees for military personnel were significantly reduced.

The state did not want to fully pay for the standing army. It was either disbanded or reassembled during hostilities. Salaries are given only for participation in battles. This greatly reduced the combat effectiveness of the troops and led to the fact that the people serving were not interested in showing enthusiasm in military service. This process reflects the general weakening of state power, which, in turn, led to Polish-Swedish intervention. Peter's military reforms of the late 17th - early 18th centuries, was accompanied by regular improvements in wages and provisions, not only for officers, but also for enlisted men and sailors. Military expenses began to occupy the main part of state expenses (78.3% in 1701). The transformation of Russia into a naval power and the almost complete absence of professional military sailors forced Peter I, tempted by high wages and low food prices (6-8 times lower than European ones), to recruit foreigners who were ready for military service.

Service in Russia. At the same time, the salary of foreigners was 1.5-2 times higher than that of Russian officers. For example, the salary of a foreign naval officer with the rank of captain of the 2nd rank was 455 rubles per year, and the salary of a Russian captain was 300 rubles; foreign navigator received 156 rubles, Russian - 120 rubles, boat - 91 and 36 rubles. In November 1706, Peter I issued a decree "On the production of salaries for the ranks of the fleet", which increased the specified amount for each sailor according to his military rank, in addition to "salary cottages in all future years" . from the amount of monthly salary. In other words, the "thirteenth wage" was introduced. In 1716-1722, Peter I issued a number of national legal documents regulating the legal basis of the official activities of military personnel, systematizing and guaranteeing their social status. Significantly, new, higher standards for military and naval ranks were established by law. This applies primarily to cash

payments and "provisions". At the same time, state-wide military personnel had to receive money first. The granting of another military rank, in particular, officer, allowed its owner to significantly improve his financial situation. For example, a lieutenant in the galley fleet received 11 times more than a midshipman; the salary of a second lieutenant was 7 times higher than that of a sergeant. Some of the money doubled. Such a serious difference in the material conditions of different categories of military personnel, of course, aroused their enthusiasm for service and the desire to constantly improve their professional training. In 1719, career creation was carried out only on the basis of competition (at least 2-3 candidates for a vacant position).

When there was a disparity between the incomes and expenses of military personnel (for example, 1722), the introduction of the "Table of colors" served as a legal basis for determining the amount of monetary allowances and determining the amount of allowances given to officers. with increased prices and the cost of services) the Admiralty Council, and then the military department sent a special dispatch to the government, for example: "... due to lack of wages, naval and admiralty employees are experiencing great difficulties..". State thanks to the measures taken by the leadership, during Peter's reign even junior officers enjoyed a very enviable position in terms of financial support. was superior to most employees of civil offices, a social group that received

In 1930, the code of benefits for servicemen of the Red Army and their families and those forced into military service was revised. It envisages the granting of benefits to military personnel in the field of social insurance and maintenance, as well as maintaining the general and continuous length of service during the period of military service. The right to preserve the housing area and its priority provision, the establishment of a preferential payment for housing, as well as a number of benefits in the provision of medical care, sanatorium-resort treatment and recreation were granted. (preferential vouchers) to both military personnel and family members of command staff. In November 1932, military pay was significantly increased by the introduction of new official salaries. By the decision of the Council of People's Commissars on August 4, 1935, a percentage increase for seniority of 5 to 25% was introduced for commanders. In 1938, a higher regular salary for command and control personnel was again established, which made it possible to increase the salary of this category by 2.9 times. Thus, in the period from 1934 to 1939. salaries of platoon commanders increased by 2.4 times, regiment commanders by 3 times, and corps commanders by 3.64 times. In the Soviet Union since the 1940s. and prior to 1991, determining the amount of pay for military personnel was based on the application of the comparative method of military labor incentives. This method was developed by the Department of Labor and Social Affairs of the Ministry of Labor of the USSR. It was based on the need to differentiate wages for workers in different sectors of the national economy based on the characteristics of work in each sector. When using this method, the salary of equivalently qualified engineers and technicians working in the defense industry was used as a guide to determine the official salaries of military personnel. Accordingly, with the increase in wages in various sectors of the national economy, the official salaries of military personnel should have increased in the same proportion.

In the conditions of the planned economy, inflationary processes were weakly expressed in the period under consideration. Until the second half of the 1980s, the average salary of military personnel was higher than the national average.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that money has a direct impact on the processes taking place in the Armed Forces. Such importance of monetary allowances given to military personnel, its

direct connection with the life and activity of the Armed Forces, their combat training, determines the introduction of amendments to the relevant legislation, the continuous improvement and development of the legal regulation in this regard. The socio-economic changes taking place in the Russian Federation, the development of free market relations, the implementation of the concept of transferring cash allowances to cash determined the decisive role of cash allowances in the system of material support of military personnel.

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